

Reflection-Refraction at an n_1 - n_2 Junction and Stable Equilibrium Like Conditions?

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The problem of a photon reflecting or refracting at an n_1 - n_2 index of refraction is solved in (1) using the notion of continuity of the electric field of a photon and its d/dx derivative for the n_1 - n_2 junction at $x=0$. The photon electric field behaves as $\cos(-\omega t+kx)$ or $\cos(-Et+px)$. We argue first of all that the photon is a quantum object and that this problem is really a quantum mechanical one as it may also be solved for a particle with rest mass using two different constant potentials V_1, V_2 instead of n_1, n_2 . In this note, we consider the photon case for convenience.

Given that the problem is really a quantum mechanical one (in our opinion), we ask: How far can one go by trying to solve it classically? We first point out that for a static uniform arrangement of objects in space, $P(x)dx = dx/L$, where L is an arbitrary length. In the case of particles moving at constant v , one may argue that each particle spends the same amount of time dt in each dx and that this also leads to a constant density in space. We suggest that for this to hold, one must consider a steady state problem and the notion of flux for physical reasons. This leads to writing the equation $1 = \text{Probability}(\text{reflect}) + \text{Probability}(\text{refract})$ as $AA/c = BB/c + CC/c_2$ where AA, BB, CC are the incident, reflected and refracted fluxes and $c_1=c, c_2=c/n_2$. We have shown in previous notes that one may mathematically write this single equation as: $A+B=C$ and $A_p-B_p = C_p^2$ using $E=pc$ (with E the same for the incident, reflected and refracted photon) and then solve the two equations for the two unknowns B, C , setting $A=1$. This approach yields a result which matches experiment, but from the standpoint of classical physics, there is no a priori reason to take the square root of flux. It simply arises as a math trick so to speak, we argue, and there seems to be no physical motivation.

Here, we suggest approaching the problem differently. We note that if $c_1-c_2 \ll 1$, then there should be almost no reflection, while if $c_2 \ll 1$, there should be almost no refraction. We ask: What happens if one suggests that in the $c_1-c_2 \ll 1$ case that one insists on BB dropping as $(c_1-c_2)^2$, i.e. to second power as in a stable equilibrium and for CC dropping as c_2^2 for $c_2 \ll 1$ in the other extreme. This is a possible approach that seems to be linked to some kind of physical principle, and one may consider the simplest solution and compare it with experiment and find that it holds. In other words, it yields the same solution as the above approaches. Moreover, this approach gives a link with the square root approach of the above paragraph, because now one is linking c_1-c_2 and c_2 directly with square root fluxes A, B, C so as to obtain the quadratic feature automatically for $c_1-c_2 \ll 1$ or $c_2 \ll 1$ when one ultimately uses AA, BB, CC . In other words, the assumption of quadratic vanishing of BB and CC , automatically leads to c_1-c_2 or c_2 vanishing of B and C , suggesting that one may automatically achieve the quadratic vanishing form by working with A, B, C square root flux variables. We suggest that this idea of quadratic vanishing of BB or CC possibly places the approach of using $A+B = C, pA-pB=p^2C$ on more physical grounds and points to a new kind of physics which uses A, B, C , namely quantum mechanics.

One Dimensional Reflection-Refraction and the Usual Approach

In (1), the problem of 1-dimensional reflection-refraction at an n_1 - n_2 junction (set at $x=0$) is solved by imposing continuity of the electric field

$$E \cos(-Et+px) \quad ((1))$$

and its derivative d/dx at $x=0$. Given that E is the same for the reflected, refracted and incident photon, one may consider $\exp(ipx)$ i.e.

$$A \exp(ipx) + B \exp(-ipx) = C \exp(ip_2x) \text{ at } x=0 \quad ((2a))$$

$$Ap \exp(ipx) - Bp \exp(-ipx) = C p_2 \exp(ip_2x) \text{ at } x=0 \quad ((2b))$$

Here A , B , C are electric field weights associated with the incident, reflected and refracted photons. Note: one may take the real part of ((2a)), ((2b)) to obtain the electric field. This leads to:

$$A+B = C \text{ and } pA-pB = p_2 C \quad ((3)) \text{ or } A p = B p + C p_2 \text{ Using } E=pc \text{ yields:}$$

$$AA/c = BB/c + CC/c_2 \text{ where } c=n_1c \text{ with } n_1=1 \text{ and } c_2=p \cdot n_2 \quad ((4))$$

We note that AA , BB , CC are associated with the square of the electric field which is fine because that is linked with energy density in electromagnetic theory. What is more interesting is that ((4)) contains $1/c$ terms, suggesting that AA , BB , CC are in fact flux values and that one is actually considering a quantum mechanical problem.

Before considering these quantum features, we note that (1) gives the values from ((4)) as

$$B/A = (c_1 - c_2) / (c_1 + c_2) \quad ((5a)) \quad C/A = 2c_2 / (c_1 + c_2) \quad ((5b))$$

Spatial Probabilities and Fluxes

We noted in the above section that AA , BB , CC are fluxes of the incident, reflected and refracted photons and so we wish to consider the physical scenario in more detail. If one has static objects uniformly distributed in one dimensional space, then:

$$P(x) dx = dx/L \text{ where } L \text{ is an arbitrary length} \quad ((6))$$

Here, however, one does not have stationary objects, but photons moving at constant speed. Thus, the physical quantity of interest is flux. At the same time, the amount of time that each photon spends in dx is a constant dt because speed is constant. If one wishes to have a static spatial probability, one must consider a steady state system with fluxes. As a result, a physical treatment of this problem should be given in terms of fluxes, we argue.

Classical Considerations Based on Conservation of Probability

One may immediately write a conservation of probability equation:

$$1 = \text{Probability}(\text{reflect}) + \text{Probability}(\text{refract}) \quad ((7))$$

We argued that physically this should be expressed in terms of fluxes, i.e.

$$AA/c = BB/c + CC/c^2 \quad ((8))$$

Here AA, BB, CC are the incident, reflected and refracted fluxes.

Mathematically, with no physical considerations, one may split ((8)) into

$$A+B=C \quad ((9a)) \quad \text{and} \quad pA - pB = p^2 C \quad ((9b))$$

One may use $E=pc$ and then solve these two equations to find the results of (1), ((5a)), ((5b))

These may be checked with experiment and found to agree. The problem is that there does not seem to be any a priori classical reason to split the two equations ((9a)) ((9b)) from ((8)). It would be nice to have some physical motivation for this. We suggest that one may possibly find such motivation without considering quantum mechanics or the photon's electric field.

Physical Consideration of Flux Behaviour

We note an interesting physical result found in ((5a)) and ((5b)):

If $(c_1 - c_2) \rightarrow 0$, then $BB = \text{reflected flux} \rightarrow 0$ as $(c_1 - c_2)^*(c_1 - c_2)$ while CC has a linear term in $(c_1 - c_2)$ ((10a))

If $c_2 \rightarrow 0$, then $CC \rightarrow 0$ as $c_2 * c_2$ while BB has a linear term in c_2 ((10b))

In other words, there seems to be an important physical result linked with fluxes which is similar to the vanishing of a dx term in a potential expansion of $V(x)$ for stable equilibrium. In particular, if one imagines a photon moving through a medium $n_1=1$, there will certainly be imperfections with n_1 fluctuating. A change in n_1 , however, should immediately give rise to a reflected photon, but physically this is probably not seen as the flux BB is suppressed due to $(c_1 - c_2)^*(c_1 - c_2)$. A similar thing happens for a particle bouncing back and forth in an n_1 region surrounded by n_2 , where n_2 is very large. Then $CC \rightarrow c_2 * c_2$ and the refracted photon is suppressed by quadratic instead of a linear term.

We suggest that this is a physical feature of nature and argue that one could in fact postulate such a feature a priori and then try to find the simplest math solution which solves the problem. One expects:

BB $\rightarrow (c_1 - c_2)^2$ for $(c_1 - c_2) > 0$, but for $c_2 \rightarrow 0$ one must obtain 1.

A possible very simple solution is: $(c_1 - c_2)^2 / \{(c_1 + c_2)(c_1 + c_2)\}$ ((11a))

Similarly, $CC \rightarrow c_2^2$ and $CC/c_2 \rightarrow 1$ for $c_1 - c_2 > 0$ and $c_1 - c_2 = \delta \ll 1$

Then $(c_1 - \delta)^2 / (c_1 - \delta)^2 = 1$

A simple solution is $function = 4 / \{(c_1 + c_2)(c_1 + c_2)\}$ to mimic ((11a))

One must then show that $AA/c = BB/c + CC/c_2$ holds in general which it does for:

$B/A = (c_1 - c_2) / (c_1 + c_2)$ and $C/A = 2c_2 / (c_1 + c_2)$ ((12))

As a result of enforcing a quadratic drop of BB in $(c_1 - c_2) \ll 1$ or of CC for $c_2 \ll 1$, one obtains a specific simple solution which may be compared with experiment. More importantly, one sees that given this quadratic feature, it seems that one should seek two linear equations in A, B, C which may then be solved to give rise to such a quadratic result for BB, CC. The quadratic feature is a physical one, we argue, and so we suggest that it gives some physical legitimacy to trying to break ((4)) into ((5a)) and ((5b)) without any notion of quantum mechanics. Giving physical legitimacy to ((5a)) and ((5b)), however, goes beyond classical physics and suggests a new kind of physics at work, namely quantum mechanics. Thus, we suggest that physical postulate that $BB \rightarrow 0$ as $(c_1 - c_2)^2$ and not $(c_1 - c_2)$ and $CC > 0$ as c_2^2 and not c_2 points in the direction of the existence of quantum mechanics.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that 1-dimensional reflection-refraction at an $n_1 - n_2$ index of refraction junction at $n_1 - n_2$ may be solved using continuity of a quantum wavefunction $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$, (with E the same for the incident, reflected, refracted photon) together with the first derivative d/dx . Alternatively (the same physics we argue), one may apply continuity of the photon electric field and continuity of d/dx as done in (1).

There are, however, other ways to solve this problem. The first is purely mathematical and seems to lack any physical motivation. Given that one physically has fluxes present, one may write $1 = P(\text{reflect}) + P(\text{refract})$ as $AA/c = BB/c + CC/c_2$ where AA, BB, CC are the incident, reflected and refracted fluxes and c_2 , the speed of light in n_2 . One may then mathematically write this as two equations using $E = pc$, $A + B = C$ and $pA - pB = p_2C$ and solve for B/A and C/A. This result matches experiment, but begs the question: Where is the underlying physics?

Here we suggest a different classical idea. We note that the solution above has BB behave as $(c_1 - c_2)^2$ and CC as c_2^2 . In the case of $(c_1 - c_2) \ll 1$, reflection is suppressed quadratically just like the quadratic term in a dx expansion of the potential $V(x)$ in a stable equilibrium. In other words, if a photon moves through an n_1 medium, there will be imperfections and changes from n_1 , but that does not mean that a reflected photon is immediately produced. Rather its production seems to be suppressed via $(c_1 - c_2)^2$.

Likewise, CC behaves as c_2^2 and for $n_2 \gg$ very large c_2^2 is a quadratic small term again. We postulate there is a physical principle indicating that BB and CC should behave quadratically in terms of $(c_1 - c_2)^2$ or c_2^2 for reasons similar to the quadratic term of dx in an expansion of $V(x)$ (potential) in a stable equilibrium situation. From this, one may actually arrive at the solution of B/A , C/A obtained via the other approaches. Furthermore, if one takes this physical postulate seriously, then it suggests that one actually solve the problem by considering equations in A, B, C to ensure a quadratic drop of $(c_1 - c_2)^2$ in BB and c_2^2 in CC . Classically, one would not consider equations linear in A, B, C and so this seems to suggest a different type of physics, namely it points to quantum mechanics, we argue.

References

1. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Reflection_phase_change